

1 **Dissecting the Genetic Control of Seed Coat Color in a RIL Population of Common**
2 **Bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.)**

3 Carmen García-Fernández, Plant Genetic Group, Regional Service for Agrofood Research and Development
4 (SERIDA), 33300, Villaviciosa, Asturias, Spain. cgarcia@serida.org

5 <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0664-796X>

6 Ana Campa, Plant Genetic Group, Regional Service for Agrofood Research and Development (SERIDA), 33300,
7 Villaviciosa, Asturias, Spain. acampa@serida.org

8 <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3970-9079>

9 Juan Jose Ferreira, Plant Genetic Group, Regional Service for Agrofood Research and Development (SERIDA),
10 33300, Villaviciosa, Asturias, Spain. jjferreira@serida.org

11 <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8782-8868>

12

13

14 For correspondence: cgarcia@serida.org

15

16 **Key message**

17 Three genes associated with the seed coat color in a TU/Musica RIL population were located on a genetic
18 map, and two candidate genes proposed to control black seed coat in the TU genotype were characterized.

19

20 **Abstract**

21 Seed coat color is an important characteristic of common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) associated with the
22 marketability of dry bean cultivars, quality and nutritional characteristics of seed, as well as response to
23 pathogens. In this study, the genetic control of seed coat color in a recombinant inbred line population (175
24 lines) obtained from the cross 'TU' x 'Musica' was investigated. Phenotypic segregation fitted 1:1 for white
25 vs. nonwhite, and 3:1 for brown vs. black, indicating the involvement of three independent genes, one
26 controlling white color and two (with epistatic interaction) controlling black color. Using a genetic map built
27 with 842 SNPs, the gene responsible for the white seed coat was mapped on the linkage group Pv07, in the
28 position previously described for the *P* gene. For the black seed coat phenotype, two genes were mapped to
29 the beginning of chromosomes Pv06 and Pv08, in the positions estimated for the *V* gene and the complex *C*
30 locus, respectively, by classical studies. The involvement of these two genomic regions was verified through
31 two crosses between three selected RILs exhibiting complementary and dominant inheritance, in which the
32 TU alleles for both genes resulted in a black phenotype. Two genes involved in the anthocyanin biosynthesis
33 pathway were proposed as candidate genes, *Phvul.006G018800* encoding a flavonoid 3'5'hydroxylase and
34 *Phvul.008G038400* encoding MYB113 transcription factor. These findings add knowledge to the complex
35 network of genes controlling seed coat color in common bean as well as providing genetic markers to be used
36 in future genetic analysis or plant breeding.

37

38 **Keywords**

39 Genetic mapping, Genotyping by sequencing (GBS); SNP; Genetic inheritance; Candidate gene; Flavonoid
40 biosynthesis pathway; Flavonoid 3',5'-hydroxylase (F3'5'H); Transcription factor MYB-113.

41

42 **Funding.** This work was supported in part by the Grant AGL2017-87050-R of the AEI-Spanish Government.

43 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program
44 under grant agreement No 774244.

45 **Conflicts of interest/Competing interests.** The authors declare that they have not conflict of interest.

46 **Ethical standard.** The authors declare that the work was original research that has not been published
47 previously, and is not under consideration for publication elsewhere.

48 **Author's Contribution.** CG-F performed the phenotyping, genomic and genetic analysis, and prepared the
49 manuscript. AC performed the genotyping and genetic analysis. JJF conceived the work and developed the
50 mapping population. All authors have read and approved the last version.

51

52 **Acknowledgments.** The authors thank M. Bueno, J.A. Poladura, and F. Díaz for their technical assistance.

53 Introduction

54 Common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) is one of the most important grain legumes and is cultivated widely
55 throughout the world (FAOSTAT 2020). Depending on the genotype, beans can be consumed as immature
56 pods (snap or green beans) or as mature seeds after re-hydration and cooking (dry beans). According to Food
57 and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) estimates, world production of dry beans for the
58 year 2019 was 28.9 million tons (FAOSTAT 2020). Bean seeds exhibit wide phenotypic diversity, including
59 variations in size, shape, and coat color, leading to many market classes. Within seed coat color variation
60 there is a wide spectrum of solid colors (white, cream, yellow, brown, red, purple, and black) of different
61 intensities, as well as patterns combining different colors (e.g., bicolor, mottled, and spotted) (Voyses, 2000).

62

63 Classical inheritance studies in common bean have described a complex network of Mendelian genes
64 controlling seed coat color with epistatic interactions among them, through which different allelic gene
65 combinations can produce the same color (Prakken 1970; Bassett 2007). Within this network of genes, there
66 is a primary or basic gene, the *P* gene (*pigment*), whose dominant genotype produces a colored seed coat
67 while the recessive genotype prevents color expression and produces a white seed coat color (Emerson 1909;
68 Kooiman 1931; McClean et al 2018). The remaining genes included in this network are classically classified as
69 follows.

70 (i) Color-determining genes including both genes that produce color and modifier genes that influence
71 (intensify or darken) the color produced by other genes. Briefly, among the 20 genes included by Bassett et
72 al. (2007) in this group are genes such as the *complex C* locus [cluster of very tightly linked genes, among
73 them, *C* (sulfur-white or primrose-yellow seed coat), *R* (dominant red color gene), *Prp* (produces black seed
74 coats in the presence of alleles of other genes), and *Gy* (controlling the change from pale greenish-yellow to
75 strong greenish-yellow seed coat color)]; the gene *B* (described as the “greenish-brown factor” that changes
76 chamois to gray-brown and also dark-violet to black seed coat); gene *G* (controlling the yellow-brown seed
77 color); gene *J* (giving light yellow-brown or pale ochraceous seed coat); gene *V* (called the “violet factor”
78 involved in the production of color ranges from pale violet to black depending upon other color genes

79 present); gene *Asp* (controlling the control brightness of the seed coat); and gene *Bic* (conferring a dark olive-
80 brown seed coat).

81 (ii) Color pattern genes such as the complex *C* locus and gene *Z* (controlling constant mottling of the seed
82 coat) the genes *T*, *Bip*, and *Fib* (controlling partly colored seed coat).

83 Some of these genes, such as *J*, *Z*, and the complex *C* locus, are involved in the control of both the color and
84 the pattern of the seed coat. Several genes controlling seed coat color or molecular markers linked to them
85 have been positioned on bean genetic maps: genes *B* (Pv02), *Z* (Pv03), *G* (Pv04), *V* (Pv06), *P* (Pv07), complex
86 *C* locus (genes *C* and *Gy*, Pv08), *T* (Pv09), *J*, and *Bip* (Pv10) (McClellan et al 2002; Hagerty et al. 2016; McClellan
87 et al 2018). Genetic mapping helps to differentiate seed coat color genes, but to clarify this complex network
88 composed of Mendelian genes with epistatic interactions, locating and characterization of the candidate
89 genes in the genome is advisable.

90
91 Seed coat color is the result of the accumulation of pigments in the coat such as flavonoids, water-soluble
92 polyphenolic compounds biosynthesized via the phenylpropanoid pathway (Beninger et al. 1999). Flavonoids
93 can be clustered into three main subclasses according to their abundance: flavonols (colorless to pale-yellow
94 pigments), anthocyanins (red to purple-black pigments), and proanthocyanidins, also called condensed
95 tannins (colorless pigments that turn brown; associated with the seed coat post-harvest darkening) (Feenstra
96 1960; Nesi et al. 2001; Caldas and Blair 2009; Elsadr et al. 2011). Much of the health benefits attributed to
97 the bean seed consumption (neuroprotective, anti-diabetic, anti-inflammatory, and anti-tumor activity,
98 among others) derive from the antioxidant activity of these secondary metabolites (Qiong-Qiong et al. 2018).

99
100 Even though the flavonoid biosynthesis pathway has been widely elucidated in different species, such as
101 *Arabidopsis thaliana* and *Glycine max*, information available in common bean is more limited (Caldas and
102 Blair 2009; Reinprecht et al. 2013; Myers et al. 2019), since to date few candidate genes have been physically
103 positioned in the genome and the implication of nucleotide allelic variations in determining seed coat color
104 has been poorly evaluated (Reinprecht et al. 2013; McClellan et al. 2018; Islam et al. 2020). Although certain

105 species-specific differences have been described, the flavonoid biosynthesis pathway presents a high degree
106 of conservation among species at both the structural and functional genetic levels (Chaves-Silva et al. 2018;
107 Petroni and Tonelli 2011). At the molecular level, the flavonoid biosynthetic pathway is organized into (i)
108 structural genes encoding enzymes that catalyze each step of the pathway, and (ii) regulatory genes
109 responsible for controlling the function of structural genes at the transcriptional level. In turn, structural
110 genes are divided into early (EBGs) and late (LBGs) biosynthetic genes (Dubos et al. 2010). Whereas EBGs
111 encode enzymes that catalyze the biosynthesis of flavones, flavonols, and other flavonoid compounds, LBGs
112 encode enzymes that specifically lead to anthocyanin and proanthocyanidin biosynthesis. The regulatory
113 genes include three families of transcription factors: R2R3-MYBs, bHLH (basic helix-loop-helix), and WD40
114 repeat transcription factors. According to the regulation pattern described in *A. thaliana*, independent R2R3-
115 MYBs are responsible for the activation of EBGs, while activation of LBGs requires the formation of ternary
116 complexes through the coupling of R2R3-MYB, bHLH, and WD40 transcription factors (MBW complexes)
117 (Petroni and Tonelli 2011).

118

119 In addition to its direct influence on the marketability of dry bean varieties and nutritional characteristics
120 (Elias et al. 2006; Rodríguez-Madrera et al. 2020), seed coat color is also linked to other seed characters. In
121 legume species, the presence of a colored seed coat is often correlated with a lower permeability to water
122 (Dübbern and Marcos-Filho 2001). This is consistent with bean seeds having a white coat requiring less
123 cooking time than those with a colored coat, especially a black coat (Cichy et al. 2015). In contrast, the lower
124 permeability attributed to the black seed coat leads to higher longevity by reducing the risk of deterioration
125 by imbibition (Dübbern and Marcos-Filho 2001). Associations between colored seed coat and emergence,
126 seed yield, and weight have also been reported in common bean (Deakin 1974; McClean et al. 2018).
127 Likewise, the coloration of the seed coat has been correlated with greater resistance to microorganism
128 attacks. Specifically, bean seeds with colored coats are associated with resistance to pathogens such as
129 potyviruses (Kyle and Dickson 1988) and *Pythium ultimum* (Campa et al. 2010).

130

131 Understanding the inheritance of seed coat color is fundamental to breeding programs involving seed coat
132 color or its pleiotropic effects on other characters. The reference genome for *P. vulgaris* (Schmutz et al. 2014)
133 provides a framework for the fine location of major genes conferring important traits and for identifying
134 candidate genes. The main aim of this work was to investigate the genetic and physical positions of genes
135 controlling seed coat color in the genotype TU through a forward genetic analysis using a recombinant inbred
136 line (RIL) population derived from the cross 'TU' x 'Musica'.

137

138 **Materials and Methods**

139 **Genetic mapping population**

140 A mapping population (TUM population) of 175 recombinant inbred lines (RILs, F_{6,7}) derived from the cross
141 'TU' (female parent) and 'Musica' (male parent), was obtained by single seed descent. The parent 'TU' is a
142 dry cultivar well known for its resistance to anthracnose disease with small (30.0 g/100 seeds) and black seed
143 coat color (Figure 1). 'Musica' is a snap bean with a medium-sized seed (45.6 g/100 seeds) and a white seed
144 coat color (Figure 1). Both parents have indeterminate growth habits and are related to the Mesoamerican
145 gene pool (Campa et al. 2018). Although, both parental lines have a majority Mesoamerican genetic
146 background, present different Andean introgression level ('TU' estimated Andean introgression level around
147 36%; 'Musica' estimated Andean introgression level less than 7%) (Campa et al. 2018).

148 The TUM population was phenotyped with the parental lines in a greenhouse using a randomized complete
149 block with a replicate per line at the Regional Agrifood Research and Development Service (SERIDA),
150 Villaviciosa, Asturias, Spain (43° 29'01'N, 5° 26'11'W; elevation 6.5m) during two consecutive seasons (2018-
151 2019). Each plot has a single 1-m row with 8-10 plants per recombinant inbred line. The seed coat color was
152 qualitatively recorded by visual examination of the seeds derived from each line and classified considering
153 the seed coat color of the two parents.

154

155 **Genotyping and SNP calling**

156 Fresh young trifoliolate leaves from each one of the 175 F₆ lines and the parental lines were collected, frozen,
157 and homogenized into a fine powder for isolating Genomic DNA using the CTAB method (Doyle and Doyle
158 1990). DNA integrity was analyzed by electrophoresis on 1% agarose gel, stained with RedSafe (iNtRON
159 Biotechnology, Gyunggi-Do, Korea), and visualized under ultraviolet light. Final DNA yield was quantified by
160 photometric absorbance at 280/260 nm using a Biomate 3 ultraviolet-visible spectrophotometer (Thermo
161 Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). DNA restriction analysis was performed on 10% of samples selected randomly
162 by digesting with *HindIII* and running on 1% agarose gel. DNA samples were preserved at -80 °C until use.

163
164 Genotyping-by-sequencing (GBS), as described by Elshire et al. (2011), was carried out at BGI-Tech
165 (Copenhagen, Denmark) using the *ApeKI* restriction enzyme. A GBS sequencing library was prepared by
166 ligating the digested DNA to unique nucleotide adapters (barcodes) followed by PCR with flow-cell
167 attachment site tagged primers. Sequencing was performed using Illumina HiSeq4000 with 100x paired-ends.
168 The sequencing reads from different genotypes were deconvoluted using the barcodes and aligned to the *P.*
169 *vulgaris* L. v2.1 (genotype G19833) reference genome (available at
170 <https://phytozome.jgi.doe.gov/pz/portal.html>), using the Burrow Wheelers Alignment tool (Li et al. 2009).
171 Single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) were named according to physical position in the bean genome:
172 chromosome and genomic position (bp). SNP markers were called using the GBS pipeline implemented in
173 TASSEL v5.2.39 software (Bradbury et al. 2007).

174 Some quality control filters were applied to avoid including variants with poor quality data. SNPs with a
175 missing rate higher than 10% and heterozygous genotypes were removed using Tassel v5.2.39 software
176 (Bradbury et al. 2007).

177

178 **Construction of genetic linkage map**

179 SNPs were filtered considering the physical distance among them and the segregation in the RIL population.
180 Those SNP markers with a physical distance less than 0.1 Mb from a neighboring marker were removed.
181 Markers showing significant deviation from the expected Mendelian segregation ratio (1:1), as determined

182 by Chi-square test ($p < 0.05$), were not considered. Linkage analysis was conducted with the R/OneMap
183 mapping package (Margarido et al. 2007; R Core Team 2020). SNPs were clustered into linkage groups (LGs)
184 using a log of likelihood ratio threshold (LOD) of 4.0 and a maximum recombination fraction (RF) of 0.35. Loci
185 order was estimated based on rapid chain delineation algorithm (Doerge 1996) and ripple analyses. Distance
186 between ordered loci (in cM) was estimated using the Kosambi mapping function. To avoid redundant
187 information, SNP blocks without observed recombination events were simplified and only one tag SNP was
188 used for map generation. Graphical visualization of the LGs was achieved by MapChart 2.32 software
189 (Voorrips 2002). The linkage groups were named according to the method described by Pedrosa-Harand et
190 al (2008).

191

192 **Genetic analysis**

193 The goodness-of-fit of observed to expected ratios was tested using chi-square tests (χ^2) considering $\alpha \leq 0.05$.

194 To map the gene(s) involved in the control of the seed coat color, a genetic analysis was performed as follows:

195 (i) In cases in which the observed segregation fit to a single gene, it was included in the genetic map.

196 (ii) When the observed segregation suggested the implication of more than one gene, contingency chi-square
197 tests were conducted for the joint segregation of seed coat color and the markers included in the genetic
198 map. A significant deviation from random segregation suggests the association of the SNPs tagging a specific
199 region with the trait. Significance thresholds were determinate using Bonferroni correction considering $\alpha =$
200 0.05 (Bonferroni, 1936).

201 Finally, complementary crosses were designed to validate the implication of candidate chromosome regions
202 in the control of seed coat color. Recombinant inbred lines (RILs) were selected according to seed coat color
203 phenotype and genotype (TU or Musica) for underlying markers tagging the candidate chromosome regions.
204 These lines were crossed to obtain F1 seeds, which were planted and self-pollinated to evaluate the seed
205 coat color of the F1 genotypes. Given the maternal inheritance of this character, the flower color phenotype
206 in the F1 plants was used as a control for successful manual cross-pollination.

207

208 **Candidate gene identification and sequencing**

209 Genes underlying significant genomic regions associated with seed coat color were identified using the
210 Phytomine tool in Phytozome v12 (<https://phytozome.jgi.doe.gov/phytomine/begin.do>). Putative candidate
211 genes were selected based on: (i) their involvement in the flavonoid biosynthesis pathway and (ii) gene-trait
212 associations previously described in the species itself (McClellan et al. 2018) or other species (Herniter et al.
213 2018).

214 Complete genomic sequences of the selected putative candidate genes were obtained from the Phytozome
215 v12 database. To resequence the candidate genes, sets of gene-specific primers pairs were designed
216 throughout their genomic sequences, seeking the maximum coverage of the coding region. Primer design
217 was carried out using BatchPrimer3 (UC Davis Server) (You et al. 2008), and potential secondary structure
218 and dimer formation were tested using OligoAnalyzer v3.1 ([http://eu.idtdna.com/
219 analyzer/Applications/OligoAnalyzer/](http://eu.idtdna.com/analyzer/Applications/OligoAnalyzer/)). DNA from parental lines ('TU' and 'Musica'), four inbred lines
220 (TUM016, TUM051, TUM101, and TUM170), and line 'G19833' (positive control) were used for resequencing.
221 PCR reactions were performed on a Verity Thermal Cycler (Applied Biosystems, Life Technologies, CA, USA)
222 using a TaKaRa LA Taq[®] kit (Clontech Laboratories, Inc., Mountain View, CA) according to the manufacturer's
223 protocol. For each reaction, 5 µL of genomic DNA (50 ng) was mixed with 5 µL of LA PCR buffer II (10x), 5 µL
224 of MgCl₂ (25 mM), 8 µL of dNTP mixture (2.5 mM each), 3 µL of each primer (10 µM), 0.5 µL of TaKaRa LA Taq
225 (5 U/ µL), and sterile purified water to a final volume of 50 µL. PCR amplification consisted of an initial
226 denaturalization step of 1 min at 94 °C, followed by 35 cycles of denaturalization at 98 °C for 10 s and gene-
227 specific annealing temperature for 5 min, and a final extension step at 72 °C for 10 min. PCR products were
228 run on a 2% agarose gel stained with RedSafe (iNTRON Biotechnology, Gyunggi-Do, Korea) and visualized
229 under ultraviolet light. Unique PCR bands were isolated and purified using Illustra™ GFX™ PCR DNA and Gel
230 Band Purification Kits (GE Healthcare Life Sciences, Buckinghamshire, UK). Purified PCR products were sent
231 for sequencing using the Sanger method to the sequencing laboratory of the University of Oviedo (Asturias,
232 Spain). The sequences obtained were analyzed by alignment with reference sequences using the BioEdit
233 sequence alignment editor v7.0.5.3 (Hall 1999; 2011). Polymorphisms identified were named according to

234 their corresponding physical position (chromosome and bp) on the reference sequence. Impacts of the
235 polymorphisms on the biological function of the proteins were predicted using Protein Variation Effect
236 Analyzer (PROVEAN) software (www.provean.jcvi.org).

237

238 **Results**

239 **Genotyping and genetic map construction**

240 Approximately 97.93 Gb of high-quality raw sequence data were obtained by GBS, and a total of 12,532 SNPs
241 were called. SNPs supplied by GBS analysis were filtered based on data completeness (> 90%), and SNPs
242 showing heterozygous genotypes were removed. A total of 8,473 SNPs distributed across the eleven bean
243 chromosomes were obtained from the TU/Musica (TUM) population. Among them, 635 showed distorted
244 segregation (χ^2 , $p < 0.01$) and 6,777 had a physical intermarker distance of less than 0.1 Mb ($\approx 80\%$), so they
245 were removed. Finally, 1,061 SNPs were used to construct the genetic linkage map. The final version of the
246 TUM linkage map contained 842 highly informative SNPs mapped to 13 linkage groups (LGs) corresponding
247 to the 11 bean chromosomes, with chromosomes Pv04 and Pv05 divided into two blocks (Table S1, Figure
248 S1). A gap in LG Pv04 was located at the end of the chromosome affecting SNPs located in the physical
249 position 37.8 Mb to 46.1 Mb. In Pv05, a gap was located near the beginning of the chromosome between the
250 SNPs with physical positions of 3.0 Mb and 7.1 Mb. The gaps found in chromosomes Pv04 and Pv05 were due
251 to the limited number of SNPs detected in those regions. In addition, LGs Pv02, Pv07, and Pv09 each included
252 one gap of more than 15 cM. The number of SNPs clustered per LG varied from 132 (Pv03) to 45 (Pv04). The
253 total genetic length of the map was 2,188.89 cM with an average intermarker distance of 3.45 cM. The length
254 of individual LGs ranged from 364.60 cM (Pv03) to 34.51 cM (Pv04).

255

256 **Seed coat color segregation**

257 The lines include in the RIL TUM population were classified into three phenotypic groups according to seed
258 coat color: white, like parental Musica (N=89); black, like parental TU (N=30); and brown (N=56) (no parental
259 phenotype) (see Figure 1). Although for genetic analysis all seeds with brown coat color were clustered into

260 a single phenotypic class, variations in color intensity among them were nevertheless observed. Segregation
261 of seed coat phenotypes was initially analyzed considering two phenotypic classes: white vs. nonwhite
262 (including brown and black phenotypes). The observed segregation fitted an expected Mendelian ratio of 1
263 (89): 1 (86) ($\chi^2 = 0.05$; $p = 0.82$), suggesting genetic control based on a single gene for the white seed coat
264 trait. For the colored subpopulation (brown vs. black), a fit to a 3 (56) :1 (30) ratio ($\chi^2 = 4.48$; $p = 0.03$) was
265 observed, suggesting that black seed coat color is determined by two independent genes with epistatic
266 effects. According to the segregation patterns obtained, the most consistent hypothesis is that three
267 independent genes control seed coat color in the TUM population.

268

269 **Mapping of seed coat color genes**

270 The white seed coat trait color, which segregated according to control by a single gene, was mapped on
271 chromosome Pv07 between SNPs S07_28535059 (291.34 cM) and S07_28968582 (298.58 cM); the
272 recombination fraction with the first flanking marker was 0.10 (LOD = 35.21). These genetic positions
273 correspond to the physical interval between 28,535,059 and 28,968,582 bp on chromosome Pv07 according
274 to the *P. vulgaris* L. v2.1 (genotype G19833) reference genome.

275

276 The phenotypic segregation ratio observed for colored seed coats suggested the involvement of two
277 independent genes. Contingency Chi-square tests revealed two genomic regions significantly associated with
278 this trait, located on chromosomes Pv06 and Pv08. The region detected on Pv06 was tagged with nine SNPs
279 located between positions 1.41 and 16.04 Mb (Table S2). Recombination events among the SNP genotypes
280 and seed coat phenotype in the colored subpopulation allowed delimiting the control of seed coat color
281 within the region flanked by markers S06_2197326 and S06_5174714 (see Figure 2). Enrichment of the
282 flanking region with six additional SNPs (filtered during the map construction) narrowed down the candidate
283 region to 2.07 Mb flanked by markers S06_2478502 and S06_4566963 (see Figure 2), corresponding to the
284 segment of chromosome Pv06 located between the physical positions 2,478,502 and 4,566,963 bp. On
285 chromosome Pv08, the region identified was tagged by a block of six SNPs located at the beginning of the

286 chromosome between 3.18 and 4.55 Mb (Table S3). Recombination events detected in six individual RILs
287 allowed to narrow the genetic region to an interval of 0.25 Mb between markers S08_3183715 and
288 S08_3430092 (Figure 2), whose physical position corresponds to 3,183,715 and 3,430,092 bp, respectively.

289

290 Finally, investigating the seed coat color phenotype and genotype in these two regions in the colored
291 subpopulation, it was observed that only the presence of the TU genotype in both candidate chromosomal
292 regions gives rise to a black seed coat color, while a Musica genotype in either region or both leads to a brown
293 seed coat color (Figure 2). This finding is consistent with the inheritance observed, suggesting two epistatic
294 and independent genes controlling black seed color in this RIL population (segregation 3 brown: 1 black).

295

296 Genetic complementation

297 To verify the presence of genes controlling seed coat color at the two candidate chromosomal regions
298 identified, two complementary crosses were performed using three selected inbred lines (TUM051, TUM101,
299 and TUM170). Selection of the lines was based on two criteria: (i) seed coat color phenotype (brown) and (ii)
300 marker genotype in the candidate regions (TU or Musica) (Figure 2). Line TUM051 had white flowers, brown
301 seed coat phenotype, and carried the Musica genotype for the markers of the candidate region on
302 chromosome Pv06 (SNP S06_2478502, S06_4221741, and S06_4566963) and the TU genotype for markers
303 of the candidate region on chromosome Pv08 (SNP S08_3183715 and S08_3430092). The recombinant lines
304 TUM101 and TUM170 presented purple flowers, brown seed coat phenotype, and carried the TU genotype
305 for the markers of the candidate chromosomal region on Pv06 (SNP S06_2478502, S06_4221741, and
306 S06_4566963), and the Musica genotype for the markers of the candidate chromosomal region on Pv08 (SNP
307 S08_3183715 and S08_3430092). Line TUM051 was used as the female parent and lines TUM101 and
308 TUM170 were used as male parents in these complementary crosses. All F1 seeds obtained (heterozygous
309 genotype) showed the brown seed coat phenotype because seed coat color is determined by the maternal
310 genotype, meaning the phenotype linked to the heterozygous genotype is expressed in the next generation.
311 A total of 14 F1 plants derived from the crosses TUM051 x TUM101 (9 plants) and TUM051 x TUM170 (5

312 plants) were self-pollinated. All F1 plants presented purple flowers, supporting their origin from a manual
313 cross-pollination, and produced F2 seeds with a black seed coat phenotype (Figure S2). This result shows that
314 the black allele has a dominant effect over the brown allele.

315 Therefore, the inheritance pattern observed was consistent with the hypothesis that two dominant and
316 complementary genes control black seed coat color in the TU genotype since only the presence of the TU
317 genotype in both chromosomal regions leads to the black color phenotype.

318

319 **Candidate genes identification**

320 The three chromosomal regions involved in the genetic control of seed coat color in the TUM population
321 were scanned in silico for underlying genes in the *P. vulgaris* L. v2.1 (genotype G19833) reference genome.

322 Lists of genes identified are provided in Tables S4, S5, and S6. The physical interval on Pv07 linked to the
323 white seed coat color contained a total of 38 genes, eight of them without functional annotation. Among the
324 set of putative candidate genes, it was found two tandem genes, *Phvul.007G171333* and *Phvul.007G171466*,
325 located at 0.20 Mb and 0.19 Mb from marker S07_28968582, respectively. Both genes are physical
326 components of the dominant-acting *P* (pigment) gene whose implication in the white seed coat phenotype
327 was previously described by McClean et al. (2018).

328

329 The two chromosomal regions associated with the presence of black seed coat color harbored a total of 75
330 annotated genes. For the region defined on Pv06, the most interesting candidate genes were
331 *Phvul.06G018800*, located close to marker S06_4221741 at a physical distance of approximately 0.11 Mb.

332 The gene *Phvul.06G018800* encodes a flavonoid 3'5' hydroxylase (F3'5'H), a cytochrome P450 enzyme
333 belonging to the CY75A subfamily that plays a key role in the anthocyanin biosynthesis pathway (see Figure
334 S3). Within the delimited region on Pv08, very close to the flanking marker S08_3188683 (at 4968 bp), it was
335 found a cluster of three genes (*Phvul.008G038400*, *Phvul.008G038500* and *Phvul.008G038600*) encoding
336 MYB-113 transcription factors with a functional annotation implicating them in the regulation of anthocyanin
337 metabolism. Alignment of multiple amino acid sequences revealed a similarity of between 40% and 53%

338 among these *MYB* genes. BlastP search in the NCBI database (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) based on the
339 protein sequences of *vigun05g039500*, a candidate gene for black seed coat color in cowpea (*Vigna*
340 *unguiculata* [L.] walp), assigned the maximum score (312; 5e-109 e-value) to *Phvul.008g038400*, with a query
341 coverage of 97% and percentage of identity of 69.10%. Based on these results, *Phvul.006G018800* and
342 *Phvul.008G038400* were initially selected as the most likely candidate genes for the control of black seed
343 coat color in the TU genotype.

344

345 **Exploring candidate gene sequences for black seed coat color**

346 A partial genomic nucleotide sequence of the two proposed candidate genes was obtained and allelic variants
347 were identified using a set of primers (Table S7) designed using G19833 as reference sequences.

348 Gene *Phvul.006G018800*: The genomic sequence of *Phvul.006G018800* spans 6,787 bp and is organized into
349 three exons and two introns flanked by 5' and 3' UTR domains in the bean reference genome (Figure 2, Table
350 S8). PCR fragments (not overlapping) resequenced for *Phvul.006G18800* for the genotypes TU and Musica
351 had a length of 4,312 bp and 3,784 bp, respectively (Figure 2, Table S8). The shorter sequence obtained from
352 Musica was due to failed amplification of two fragments (sequencing gaps), one located in intron 2 and the
353 other in the 3' UTR domain, according to the reference gene sequence. Nevertheless, the resequenced
354 fragments included a full-length coding sequence composed of three exons, similar to the reference gene, in
355 both parental lines (Figure 3; Table S8). Alignment of sequences obtained from the genotypes G19833, TU,
356 and Musica revealed more than one hundred polymorphic positions, among which are included a single base
357 pair deletion in exon 3 at position 6,125 in the TU and Musica genotypes (Figure S4). Nevertheless, the
358 majority of the polymorphisms detected resulted in variations between G19833 and the parental lines. TU
359 and Musica showed a high level of genomic nucleotide sequence conservation (96.5 % identity), with only
360 eight nucleotide differences identified, out of which, based on the reference gene structure, six were located
361 in intron regions, one in exon 3, and one in 3' UTR domain. The coding variant (SNP06_6032G/A) involved a
362 single base pair substitution that leading to a homologous amino acid replacement from serine (TU) to
363 asparagine (Musica) at position 327 aa of the predicted protein sequence. PROVEAN analysis suggested a

364 neutral functional effect associated with this amino acid change (score = -1.087; cut off= -2.5). The
365 polymorphism in the 3' UTR involved a deletion of 14 bp (DEL06_6296-6309) located close to the beginning
366 of the region, which affects the binding site of the primer Phvul.006G018800_F11.

367

368 Gene Phvul.008G038400: The genomic sequence for *Phvul.008G038400* is 2,275 nucleotides in length and
369 shares a similar structure with *Phvul.006G018800*, consisting of three exons and two introns flanked by the 5'
370 and 3' UTR domains. To avoid the interference of non-specific amplification resulting from the presence of
371 regions highly conserved among different *MYB* genes, resequencing of *Phvul.008G038400* involved a single
372 amplicon using the flanking primers (*Phvul.008G038400_F1* and *Phvul.008G038400_R4*) designed from the
373 intergenic regions (see Figure 3). This strategy allowed isolating the complete sequence of *Phvul.008G038400*
374 for the lines G19833 (used as a positive control) and the TU genotype. The length of the partial sequence
375 obtained for the TU genotype was 1,591 bp, covering the complete gene sequence except for a gap in the
376 second intron (Figure 2; Table S8). It was not possible to amplify the Musica genotype using the same flanking
377 primers. The longest amplicon isolated for this line was extended from the 5' intergenic
378 ((*Phvul.008G038400_E1_F*) region to exon 2 (*Phvul.008G038400_E2_R*), and the sequence obtained was only
379 392 bp in length (Figure 2; Table S8). Multiple sequence alignment revealed high levels of polymorphism
380 (Figure S5). Around 60% of the polymorphisms identified represented allelic variations between the two
381 parental lines, distributed throughout the 5'UTR (6), exon 1 (16), intron 1 (29), and exon 2 (1) (partially
382 resequenced) based on the reference gene structure (Figure S5).

383

384 **Gene marker genotyping**

385 The observed allelic variation was used to develop markers tagging both candidate genes. The differences in
386 amplification [presence (TU) / absence (Musica)] detected for the 3'UTR of *Phvul.006G188000* and for the
387 amplicon that included the complete gene sequence of *Phvul.008G038400* were selected as direct gene
388 markers by tagging allelic variations existing between the two genotypes (Figure 4, Table S7). The gene
389 markers were called BSC06 and BSC08, respectively, in reference to the Black Seed Coat trait and their

390 chromosomal location. Both markers co-segregated with the SNPs tagging in the respective regions (see
391 Figure 2). BSC06 co-segregated with the SNP06_4221741 except in one line, whereas BSC08 co-segregated
392 with SNP07_3183715 except in two lines. All TUM lines with black seed coat phenotype showed TU genotype
393 for both gene markers, whereas lines with a brown seed coat phenotype presented Musica genotype for at
394 least one of the two markers (Figure 4).

395

396 Discussion

397 A complex network of genes is implicated in the genetic control of seed coat color in common bean (Bassett
398 2007). In this work, the genetic control of the seed coat color, as well as the location in the genetic and
399 physical map, was investigated in an F_{6:7} TUM RIL population obtained from the cross 'TU' x 'Musica'.
400 Genotyping of the TUM RIL population was based on 12,532 SNPs obtained from a GBS approach. Filtering
401 criteria applied for strict selection of highly-quality SNPs allowed the construction of a genetic linkage map
402 composed of 842 SNPs markers that covering the 11 LGs. Two major gaps were detected on the linkage
403 groups LGs Pv04 and Pv05, indicating that these regions were highly conserved between the two parental
404 lines. This finding is in agreement with the common Mesoamerican origin of their genetic background
405 reported by Campa et al (2018). 'Musica' is a snap bean derived from breeding programs, which is included
406 in the Mesoamerican gene pool, whereas 'TU' is a dry bean included in a recombinant group between
407 Mesoamerican and Andean gene pools. Consequently, less polymorphism is expected for this population
408 than for populations derived from crosses between lines belonging to different gene pools (Mesoamerican
409 vs Andean).

410

411 In this work, the inheritance of the seed coat color was evaluated as a qualitative character since different
412 phenotypic classes were clearly established in the recombinant lines. The results obtained for the TUM RIL
413 population indicated the involvement of three independent genes with epistatic interaction in the control of
414 the three seed coat color phenotypic classes observed: white, brown, and black. White seed coat color is
415 regulated by a single gene located in a physical interval between 28,535,059 and 28,968,582 bp on

416 chromosome Pv07. Among the genes in this interval are *Phvul.007G171333* and *Phvul.007G171466*, two
417 physical components of a single-gene model characterized by McClean et al. (2018) as the *P* gene in common
418 bean. The *P* gene encodes a TT8 bHLH transcription factor, a key component of the MBW complex that
419 regulates activation of the flavonoid biosynthetic pathway (McClean et al. 2018). This annotation is consistent
420 with the classical concept that defined *P* as a dominant basic gene that does not produce any color by itself,
421 but whose presence is necessary to produce seeds with colored coats (Prakken 1970, 1972). Recessive alleles
422 of the *P* gene [*p*] shut down the flavonoid biosynthesis pathway at a primary level; consequently, a
423 biochemical profile characterized by the absence of flavonols and anthocyanins is responsible for the
424 completely white seed coat phenotype (Rodríguez-Madrera et al. 2020). McClean et al. (2018) identified 10
425 race-specific *P* alleles involved in the expression of the white seed coat phenotype. These alleles are
426 characterized by nucleotide variations resulting in deletions located in the functional protein domain,
427 deletions that truncates the translation product prematurely, and non-synonymous coding SNPs responsible
428 for substitution of essential amino acid residues that compromise the protein function.

429
430 Concerning to black seed coat phenotype, the results indicated that is controlled by two independent genes
431 located at the beginning of the chromosomes Pv06 and Pv08, with epistatic interaction. Physical delimitation
432 within the bean genome allowed to locate the first gene between positions 2,478,502 and 4,566,963 bp of
433 chromosome Pv06, and the second gene between positions 3,183,715 and 3,430,092 bp of chromosome
434 Pv08. This analysis also revealed that the black seed coat phenotype results from the presence of a TU
435 genotype in both chromosomal regions. This complementarity of the chromosomal regions identified was
436 evidenced by the results of crosses between three inbred lines showing a brown seed coat color phenotype
437 and complementary genotypes. The complementarity test also determined that black seed coat color is
438 controlled by dominant alleles at both loci (black > brown). McClean et al. (2002) positioned the marker
439 OD12₈₀₀ (physical position, 9.4 Mbp) at the beginning of chromosome Pv06 by genetic linkage to the *V* gene,
440 also known as the violet factor (Prakken 1970). Classical genetic studies described the *V* gene as a color
441 enhancer or modifier gene which has multiple alleles with pleiotropic effects on color in flowers and seed

442 coats (Prakken 1970; 1974; Bassett 1993, 1997; Bassett and Miklas 2007). Specifically, the [V] allele produces
443 seed coats in which color ranges from pale violet to black depending upon other color genes present
444 (Lamprecht 1932; Prakken 1934, 1972), whereas the [v] allele (in the presence of other color genes like T P C
445 J G B) produces mineral brown seed coat (Lamprecht 1935; Bassett and Miklas 2007). Beninger et al. (1999;
446 2000) affirmed that anthocyanin production is dependent on the V gene, since the presence of dominant
447 genotypes [V] leads to anthocyanin accumulation, whereas recessive genotypes [v] lead to flavonol
448 accumulation. McClean et al. (2002) also mapped the complex C locus to the beginning of chromosome Pv08
449 through the markers OW17S₆₀₀ (physical position, 3.2 Mbp) and OAP2₇₀₀ (physical position, 9.6 Mbp) linked
450 to the C and Gy genes, respectively. Although most studies correlate the function of the complex C locus with
451 the control of a wide diversity of patterns in common bean seed coats (Prakken 1974), Bassett (1994)
452 established a tight linkage of the black seed coat color trait and the complex C locus in the presence of other
453 dominant alleles of color genes, including P and V. Thus, the genetic location of the V gene and the complex
454 C locus, allows to speculate on their possible connection with the Pv06 and Pv08 chromosome regions
455 identified in the present study, respectively.

456

457 In the tagged region of chromosome Pv06, it was found the annotated gene *Phvul0006G18800*, one EBG gene
458 encoding an F3'5'H enzyme, which plays a crucial role in the branch of the flavonoid biosynthesis pathway
459 leading to delphinidin-based production of anthocyanins (blue/purple pigments) (Figure S3). This finding
460 supports black seed coat phenotypes resulting from a biochemical composition profile characterized by high
461 anthocyanin accumulation (Takeoka et al. 1997, Díaz et al. 2010, Rodríguez-Madrera et al. 2020). The
462 biosynthetic pathway leading to delphinidin-based anthocyanins appears to be the main way of producing
463 black seed coat color in common bean (Takeoka et al. 1997, Díaz et al. 2010, Rodríguez-Madrera et al. 2020),
464 although black color could also be produced by the accumulation of different anthocyanin classes (Rodríguez-
465 Madrera et al. 2020). The resequencing of *Phvul.006G18800* revealed eight polymorphic positions between
466 the two parental genotypes, highlighting a non-synonymous coding SNP (SNP_6032G/A) and a deletion of 14
467 bp (DEL06_6296-6309), located in exon 3 and 3'UTR, respectively, according to the gene structure established

468 for G19833. Although expression and functional studies are required to determine the possible implications
469 of these polymorphic positions, everything seems to indicate that the presence of recessive Musica alleles in
470 *Phvul.006G18800* [*musica*] would inhibit expression of the black seed coat phenotype by blocking the main
471 anthocyanins biosynthesis pathway in the TUM lines (Figure S3). Therefore, the TU and Musica genotype are
472 consistent with genotypic implications described for the dominant [*V* = *TU*] and recessive [*v* = *musica*] alleles
473 of the *V* gene (Beininger et al. 1999; 2000). The involvement of *F3'5'H* in the control of black seed coat
474 coloration has also been described in soybean (*Glycine max* and *Glycine soja*) by means of the *W1* gene
475 (Zabala and Vodkin 2007; Guo and Qiu 2013). Furthermore, the comparison of the genomic maps of soybean
476 and common bean showed that the genomic position to which the *W1* gene was mapped (Gm13) is syntenic
477 to the region of common bean where the *F3'5'H* gene is located at the top of chromosome Pv06 (Reinprecht
478 et al. 2013).

479

480 Within the Pv08 chromosomal region identified, it was found a cluster of three genes members of the MYB
481 family of transcription factors (*MYB113*) involved in the regulation of anthocyanin biosynthesis (Gonzalez et
482 al. 2008). Within this *MYB113* cluster is included *Phvul.008G038400*, an ortholog gene of *Vigun05G039500*,
483 proposed as a candidate gene for black seed coat color in cowpea (Herniter et al. 2018). In *A. thaliana*, the
484 *MYB113* gene is included within the subgroup of R2R3-MYBs in charge of regulating the expression of
485 enzymes involved in the last steps of the anthocyanin biosynthesis pathway in vegetative tissues (LBG gene)
486 (Gonzalez et al. 2008). Thus, *Phvul.008G038400* would be acting on the final key step leading to anthocyanin
487 accumulation and, consequently, towards the black seed coat phenotype in the TUM population. In addition,
488 this late regulation by *Phvul.008G038400* is consistent with the observation that within the brown phenotypic
489 class, darker brown seed coats corresponded to TUM lines carrying the TU genotype for *Phvul.006G18800*
490 and the Musica genotype for *Phvul.008G038400*. On the other hand, the identification of a cluster of MYB
491 genes involved in anthocyanin biosynthesis agrees with the classical interpretation that describes complex *C*
492 locus as a group of closed linked genes involved in the determination of seed coat color phenotype (Prakken
493 1974).

494

495 The nucleotide sequences obtained from the resequencing of *Phvul.008G038400* showed a low conservation
496 degree between the TU and Musica genotypes, and also concerning the reference sequence of G19833. The
497 main difference was that while for the TU genotype a complete gene sequence was amplified, only a partial
498 amplification (from 5' intergenic region up to the second exon) was achieved for the Musica genotype. This
499 is similar to results obtained by Herniter et al. (2018) for *Vigun05G039500* in cowpea, who described
500 consistent, successful amplification of a fragment of the third exon in all lines with black seed coats and a
501 similarly consistent failure to amplify this fragment in lines with brown seed coats. These authors described
502 a deletion of approximately 41 kb that involving *Vigun05G039500* as well as other nearby *MYB* genes and
503 whose origin could be due to non-allelic homologous recombination, an unequal crossover between highly
504 similar DNA sequences. Similar to *Vigun05G039500*, *Phvul.008G038400* belongs to a gene cluster of five
505 *MYB113*-related genes; two genes are located downstream and included among the genes within the region
506 identified (*Phvul.008G038500* and *Phvul.008G038600*), and two genes are located upstream, outside of the
507 associated chromosomal region (*Phvul.008G038000* and *Phvul.008G038200*). According to the results
508 obtained and the high similarity between common bean and cowpea, the absence of amplification in the
509 Musica genotype could correspond to the presence of a deletion similar to that described in cowpea. In
510 addition, since *Phvul.008G038400* is part of a cluster of genes, the detected polymorphism could act not only
511 as a specific marker of the gene but also of the MYB cluster.

512

513 On the other hand, from the polymorphism detected between the TU and Musica genotypes for the
514 candidate genes *Phvul.06G011880* and *Phvul.008G038400*, two user-friendly markers (BSC06 and BSC08,
515 respectively) were developed. BSC06 and BSC08, constitute gene-specific markers, which are advantageous
516 over linked markers since possible recombination processes between marker and gene are avoided, and thus
517 the selection of false positives in marker-assisted selection in breeding programs.

518

519 Thus, in the TU x Musica genomic background, three genes, *Phvul.007G171333-Phvul.007G171466*
520 (components of the same gene), *Phvul. 006G018800*, and *Phvul.008G038400*, which appear to be related to
521 the classical genes *P*, *V*, and the complex *C* locus, respectively, would be regulated the expression of the
522 different seed coat phenotypes observed. The presence of the recessive genotype of the *P* gene [*p^{musica}*]
523 causes any genotypic combination to confer a white seed coat phenotype. However, in the presence of the
524 *P* dominant allele [*P^{TU}*], the interaction between the *V* [*V^{TU}*] and the complex *C* [*C^{TU}*] alleles, leads to a black
525 seed coat phenotype [*P^{TU} V^{TU} C^{TU}*], whereas the remaining gene combinations give rise to a brown seed coat
526 phenotype [*P^{TU} V^{TU} c^{musica}*] or [*P^{TU} v^{musica} C^{TU}*].

527

528 **Conclusions**

529 This work verified the genetic and genomic position of the *P* gene in common bean. Likewise, it was
530 determined the genetic and genomic position of two dominant and complementary genes controlling the
531 black seed color in the TU genotype at the beginning of chromosomes Pv06 and Pv08. Finally, this work
532 provides two **user-friendly** markers (BSC06 and BSC08) **to assist** future genetic analysis or plant breeding.

533 This finding adds knowledge for elucidating the complex network of genes involved in the control of seed
534 coat color determination in common bean. **Nevertheless, additional forward genetic analysis should be**
535 **carried out to locate the genomic position of the remaining seed coat color loci. Likewise, analysis of gene**
536 **expression in the developing seed can be another alternative way to identify/validate new candidate genes**
537 **controlling seed coat color in common bean.**

538

539 **References**

540 Bassett MJ (1994) Tight linkage of purple pod character and the complex C locus in common bean. The Journal
541 of Heredity 85(4):288-290. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordjournals.jhered.a111458>

542 Bassett MJ (2007) Genetics of seed coat color and pattern in common bean. Plant Breeding Reviews 28:239-
543 315. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470168028.ch8>

544 Bassett MJ, Miklas PN (2007) A new gene, *bic*, with pleiotropic effects with (T P V) for bicolor flowers and
545 dark olive-brown seed coat in common bean. Journal of the American Society for Horticultural
546 Science 132:352-356. <https://doi.org/10.21273/JASHS.132.3.352>

547 Beninger CW, Hosfield GL, Bassett MJ (1999) Flavonoid composition of three genotypes of dry bean
548 (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) differing in seed coat color. Journal of the American Society for Horticultural
549 Science 124:514-518. <https://doi.org/10.21273/JASHS.124.5.514>

550 Beninger CW, Hosfield GL, Bassett MJ, Owens S. (2000) Chemical and morphological expression of the B and
551 Asp seedcoat genes in *Phaseolus vulgaris* L. Journal of the American Society for Horticultural Science,
552 125: 52-58. <https://doi.org/10.21273/JASHS.125.1.52>

553 Bonferroni CE (1936) Teoria statistica delle classi e calcolo delle probabilita. Pubblicazioni del R Istituto
554 Superiore di Scienze Economiche e Commerciali di Firenze 8: 3-62.

555 Bradbury PJ, Zhang Z, Kroon DE, Casstevens TM, Ramdoss Y, Buckler ES (2007) TASSEL: Software for
556 association mapping of complex traits in diverse samples. Bioinformatics 23:2633-2635.
557 <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btm30>

558 Caldas GV, Blair MW (2009) Inheritance of seed condensed tannins and their relationship with seed-coat
559 color and pattern genes in common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.). Theoretical and Applied Genetics
560 119:137-142. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00122-009-1023-4>

561 Campa A, Pérez-Vega E, Pasucal A, Ferreira JJ (2010) Genetic analysis and molecular mapping of a quantitative
562 trait loci in common bean against *Pythium ultimum*. Phytopathology 100(12):1315-1320.
563 <https://doi.org/10.1094/PHYTO-06-10-0161>

564 Campa A, Murube E, Ferreira, JJ (2018) Genetic diversity, population structure and linkage disequilibrium in
565 a Spanish common bean diversity panel revealed through Genotyping-by-Sequencing. Genes
566 9(11):518. <https://doi.org/10.3390/genes9110518>

567 Chaves-Silva S, dos Santos AL, Chanfun-Júnior A, Zhao J, Peres LE, Benedito VA (2018) Understanding the
568 genetic regulation of anthocyanin biosynthesis in plants - Tools for breeding purple varieties of fruits
569 and vegetables. *Phytochemistry*, 153, 11-27. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phytochem.2018.05.013>

570 Cichy KA, Wiesinger JA, Mendoza, FA (2015) Genetic diversity and genome-wide association analysis of
571 cooking time in dry bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.). *Theoretical and Applied Genetics* 128(8):1555-1567.
572 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00122-015-2531-z>

573 Deakin JR (1974) Association of seed color with emergence and seed yield of snap beans. *Journal of the*
574 *American Society for Horticultural Science* 99(2):110-114.

575 Díaz AM, Caldas GV, Blair MW (2010) Concentrations of condensed tannins and anthocyanins in common
576 bean seed coats. *Food Research International* (43) 595-601.
577 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2009.07.014>

578 Doerge RW (1996) Constructing genetic maps by rapid chain delineation. *Journal of Quantitative Trait Loci*
579 2:121-31.

580 Doyle JJ, Doyle LH (1990) Isolation of plant DNA from fresh tissue. *Focus* 12:13-15.

581 Dübbern FH, Marcos-Filho J (2001) The seed coat as a modulator of seed-environment relationships in
582 Fabaceae. *Brazilian Journal of Botany* 24(4):365-375. [https://doi.org/10.1590/S0100-](https://doi.org/10.1590/S0100-84042001000400002)
583 [84042001000400002](https://doi.org/10.1590/S0100-84042001000400002)

584 Dubos C, Stracke R, Grotewold E, Weisshaar B, Martin C, Lepiniec L. (2010). MYB transcription factors in
585 *Arabidopsis*. *Trends in Plant Science* 15:573-581. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tplants.2010.06.005>

586 Elias LG, De Fernandez DG, Bressani RJ. (2006). Possible effects of seed coat polyphenolics on the nutritional
587 quality of bean protein. *Journal of Food Science* 44(2):524-527. [https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2621.1979.tb03827.x)
588 [2621.1979.tb03827.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2621.1979.tb03827.x)

589 Elsadr HT, Wright LC, Pauls KP, Bett KE (2011) Characterization of seeds coat post-harvest darkening in
590 common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.). Theoretical and Applied Genetics 123(8):1467-1472.
591 [https://doi.org/ 10.1007/s00122-011-1683-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00122-011-1683-8)

592 Elshire RJ, Glaubitz JC, Sun Q, Poland JA, Kawamoto K, Buckler ES, Mitchell SE (2011) A robust, simple
593 genotyping-by-sequencing (GBS) approach for high diversity species. PLoS ONE 6:e19379.
594 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0019379>

595 Emerson R(1909) Factors for mottling in beans. Journal of Heredity 5(1):368-375.
596 <https://doi.org/10.1093/jhered/os-5.1.368>

597 FAO (2020) <http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QC>. Last accessed March 2021

598 Feenstra WJ (1960) Biochemical aspect of seedcoat colour inheritance in *Phaseolus vulgaris* L. Meded
599 Landbouwhogeschool Wageningen(60):1-53. Retrieved from <https://edepot.wur.nl/183363>

600 Gonzalez A, Zhao M, Leavitt JM, Lloyd AM (2008) Regulation of the anthocyanin biosynthetic pathway by the
601 TTG1/bHLH/MYB transcriptional complex in *Arabidopsis* seedlings. Plant Journal 53:814-827.
602 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-313X.2007.03373.x>

603 Guo Y, Qiu LJ (2013) Allele-specific marker development and selection efficiencies for both flavonoid 3'-
604 hydroxylase and flavonoid 3',5'-hydroxylase genes in soybean subgenus soja. Theoretical Applied
605 Genetics 126:1445–1455. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00122-013-2063-3>

606 Hagerty C, Cuesta-Marcos A, Cregan P, et al (2016) Mapping Snap Bean Pod and Color Traits, in a Dry Bean ×
607 Snap Bean Recombinant Inbred Population. Journal of the American Society for Horticultural Science
608 141(2):131-138. <https://doi.org/10.21273/JASHS.141.2.131>

609 Hall TA (1999) BioEdit: a user-friendly biological sequence alignment editor and analysis program for
610 Windows 95/98/NT. Nucleic Acids Symposium, 41, 95-98.
611 https://doi.org/10.14601/Phytopathol_Mediterr-14998u1.29

- 612 Hall TA (2011) BioEdit: an important software for molecular biology. GEF bulletin of Bioscience 2:60-61.
- 613 Herniter IA, Muñoz-Amatriaín M, Lo S, Go Y-N, Close TJ (2018) Identification of candidate genes controlling
614 black seed coat and pod tip color in cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* [L.] walp). G3: Genes, Genomes,
615 Genetics, 10:3347-3355. <https://doi.org/10.1534/g3.118.200521>
- 616 Islam N, Bett K, Pauls K, Marsolais F, Dhaubhadel S (2020) Postharvest seed coat darkening in pinto bean
617 (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) is regulated by Psd, an allele of the basic helix-loop-helix transcription factor P.
618 New Phytologist Foundation 2(6):663-677. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ppp3.10132>
- 619 Kooiman H (1931) Monograph on the genetics of *Phaseolus* (especially *Ph. vulgaris* and *Ph. multiflorus*).
620 Bibliographica Genetica VIII 295-413.
- 621 Kyle MM, Dickson MH (1988) Linkage of hypersensitivity to five viruses with the locus in *Phaseolus vulgaris*
622 L. Journal of Heredity 79(4):308-311. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordjournals.jhered.a110516>
- 623 Lamprecht H (1932). Beitrage zur Genetik von *Phaseolus vulgaris*. Zur Vererbung der Testafarbe. Hereditas
624 16:169-211.
- 625 Lamprecht H (1935) Zur Genetik von *Phaseolus vulgaris*. XII. Über die Vererbung der Blütenund Stammfarbe.
626 Hereditas 21:129-166.
- 627 Li H, Durbin R (2009) Fast and accurate short read alignment with Burrows-Wheeler transform.
628 Bioinformatics 25:1754-1760. <https://doi.org/10.1090/bioinformactics/btm308>
- 629 Margarido GR, Souza AP, Garcia AA (2007) OneMap: software for genetic mapping in outcrossing species.
630 Hereditas 144:78-79. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2007.0018-0661.02000.x>
- 631 McClean PE, Lee RK, Otto C, Gepts P, Bassett MJ (2002) Molecular and phenotypic mapping of genes
632 controlling seed coat pattern and color in common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.). The Journal of
633 Heredity 93:148-152. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jhered/93.2.148>

634 McClean PE, Bett KE, Stonehouse R, Lee R, Pflieger, S, et al (2018) White seed color in common bean
635 (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) results from convergent evolution in the P (pigment) gene. *New Phytologist*
636 219:1112-1123. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.15259>

637 Myers J, Wallace L, Moghaddam S, et al (2019) Improving the Health Benefits of Snap Bean: Genome-Wide
638 Association Studies of Total Phenolic Content. *Nutrients* 11:2509.
639 <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu11102509>.

640 Nesi N, Jond C, Debeaujon K, Caboche M, Lepiniec L (2001) The Arabidopsis TT2 gene encodes an R2R3 MYB
641 domain protein that acts as a key determinant for proanthocyanidin accumulation in developing
642 seed. *Plant Cell* 13:2099-2114. <https://doi.org/10.1105/TPC.010098>

643 Pedrosa-Harand A, Porch T, Gepts P (2007) Standard nomenclature for common bean chromosomes and
644 linkage groups. *Annual Report of the Bean Improvement Cooperative* 51.

645 Petroni K, Tonelli C (2011) Recent advances on the regulation of anthocyanin synthesis in reproductive
646 organs. *Plant Science* 181:219-229. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.plantsci.2011.05.009>

647 Phytozome (2020) Retrieved from Plant Comparative Genomics portal of the Department of Energy's Joint
648 Genome Institute. http://phytozome.jgi.doe.gov/pz/portal.html#!info?alias=Org_Pvulgaris

649 Prakken R (1934) Inheritance of colors and pod characters in *Phaseolus vulgaris* L. *Genetica* 16:177-294.
650 <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02071498>

651 Prakken R (1970) Inheritance of colour in *Phaseolus vulgaris* L. II. A critical review. *Meded.*
652 *Landbouwhogeshool Wageningen* 70(23):1-38.

653 Prakken R (1972) Inheritance of colour in *Phaseolus vulgaris* L. III. On genes for red seed-coat colour and a
654 general synthesis. *Meded. Landbouwhogeshool Wageningen* 72(29):1-82.

655 Prakken R(1974) Inheritance of colours in *Phaseolus vulgaris* L. IV. Recombination within the "complex locus
656 C". *Meded Landbouwhogeshool Wageningen* 24:1-36.

657 Qiong-Qiong Y, Ren-You G, Ying-Ying G, Dan Z, Harold C (2018) Polyphenols in common beans (*Phaseolus*
658 *vulgaris* L.): chemistry, analysis, and factors affecting composition. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food*
659 *Science and Food Safety* 17(6):1518-1539. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1541-4337.12391>

660 R Core Team (2020) R: A Language and environment for statistical computing R Foundation for Statistical
661 Computing Vienna Austria. Retrieved March 31, 2020, from <http://www.r-project.org/index.html>

662 Reinprecht Y, Yadegari Z, Perry GE, Siddiqua M, Wright L, McClean PE, Pauls KP (2013) In silico comparison of
663 genomic regions containing genes coding for enzymes and transcription factors for the
664 phenylpropanoid pathway in *Phaseolus vulgaris* L. and *Glycine max.* L. Merr. *Frontiers in Plant Science*
665 4:317. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2013.00317>

666 Rodríguez-Madrera R, Campa A, Suárez BV, Ferreira JJ (2020) Characterization of extractable phenolic profile
667 of common bean seeds (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) in a Spanish diversity panel. *Food Research*
668 *International*,138(Pt A):109713. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2020.109713>

669 Schmutz J, McClean P, Mamidi SE (2014) A reference genome for common bean and genome-wide analysis
670 of dual domestications. *Nature Genetics* 46:707-713. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ng.3008>

671 Takeoka GR, Dao LT, Full GH, Wong RY, Harden LA, Edwards RH, Berrios JD (1997) Characterization of black
672 bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) anthocyanins. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry* 45(9):3395-
673 3400. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf970264d>

674 Voorrips R (2002) MapChart: software for the graphical presentation of linkage maps and QTLs. *Journal of*
675 *Heredity* 93:277-285. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jhered/93.1.77>

676 Voysest O (2000) Mejoramiento genético del frijol (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) : Legado de variedades de América
677 Latina 1930-1999. Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical (CIAT), Cali, CO (Publicación CIAT no.
678 321). Retrieved from <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/54161>

679 You FM, Huo N, Gu YQ, Luo M, Ma Y, Hane D, et al (2008) BatchPrimer3: A high throughput web application
680 for PCR and sequencing primer design. BMC Bioinformatics 9:253. [https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-](https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2105-9-253)
681 [2105-9-253](https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2105-9-253)

682 Zabala G, Vodkin L (2007) A rearrangement resulting in small tandem repeats in the F3'5'H gene of white
683 flower genotypes is associated with the soybean W1 locus. Crop Science 113-124.
684 <https://doi.org/10.2135/cropsci2006.12.0838tpg>

685

686 **Figure caption**

687 **Figure 1.** Seeds of the parental lines TU and Musica and the TUM RILs analyzed (one seed per RIL).

688

689 **Figure 2.** Comparison among seed coat color phenotype and genotype for the SNP tagging the candidate
690 regions in the TUM sub-population with colored seeds. Each column represents a line. Black boxes indicate
691 the genotype TU; brown boxes indicate the genotype Musica and white boxes indicate missing genotypes
692 data. The two gene markers developed from the gene sequences *Phvul.006G018800* (BSC06) and
693 *Phvul.008G038400* (BSC08) (highlighted in red) are included.

694

695 **Figure 3.** Diagrammatic representation of resequencing coverage of the genes *Phvul.006G018800* and
696 *Phvul.008G038400* using G19833 as reference sequence. The position of primers used for resequencing and
697 primers used as gene markers (BSC06 and BSC08) are also indicated.

698

699 **Figure 4.** Gene markers used to differentiate the genotypes TU and Musica in the colored TUM
700 subpopulation. (A) Amplification pattern obtained from *BSC06*. (B) Amplification pattern obtained from
701 *BSC08*.

702

703

704 **Electronic supplementary material**

705 **Supplementary Figure S1.** Genetic linkage map developed in the recombinant inbred TUM population from
706 842 SNPs obtained from genotyping-by-sequencing.

707

708 **Supplementary Figure S2.** F2 progenies obtained from the complementary crosses between selected TUM
709 RILs: TUM051xTUM101 and TU051xTUM170. Labels in the seed progenies (F2 seeds) imagines indicate the
710 ID of the F1 plant by which they were produced.

711

712 **Supplementary Figure S3.** A simple schematic diagram of flavonoid biosynthesis pathway [adapted from
713 Petroni and Tornelli (2011) and Reinprecht et al. (2013)].

714

715 **Supplementary Figure S4.** Multiple sequence alignment of *Phvul.006G018800* gene for the genotypes TU and
716 Musica using G19833 as reference sequence. Points indicate identical residues. 'N' represents nucleotide
717 positions not determined in this study. Coding regions are highlighted in yellow boxes.

718

719 **Supplementary Figure S5.** Multiple sequence alignment of *Phvul.008G038400* gene for the genotypes TU and
720 Musica using G19833 as reference sequence. Points indicate identical residues. 'N' represents nucleotide
721 positions not determined in this study. Coding regions are highlighted in yellow boxes.

722

723 **Supplementary Table S1.** Linkage map summary information for the TUM RIL population. Tag SNPs indicate
724 the number of SNPs included in the genetic map.

725

726 **Supplementary Table S2.** Results to contingency Chi-square tests between seed coat color phenotype (black
727 vs brown) and the SNPs mapped on chromosome Pv06 in the TUM RIL subpopulation of colored seeds.
728 Significant associations (highlighted in bold) were considered after application of Bonferroni correction ($\alpha =$
729 0.05; P-value $\leq 5.9384E-05$).

730

731 **Supplementary Table S3.** Results to contingency Chi-square tests between seed coat color phenotype (black
732 vs. brown) and the SNPs mapped on chromosome Pv08 in the TUM RIL subpopulation of colored seeds.
733 Significant associations (highlighted in bold) were considered after application of Bonferroni correction ($\alpha =$
734 0.05; P-value $\leq 5.9384E-05$).

735

736 **Supplementary Table S4.** List of annotated genes found for the bounded region in the chromosome Pv07
737 from the reference genome (available at <https://phytozome.jgi.doe.gov/pz/portal.html>).

738

739 **Supplementary Table S5.** List of annotated genes found for the bounded region in the chromosome Pv06
740 from the reference genome (available at <https://phytozome.jgi.doe.gov/pz/portal.html>).

741

742 **Supplementary Table S6.** List of annotated genes found for the bounded region in the chromosome Pv08
743 from the reference genome (available at <https://phytozome.jgi.doe.gov/pz/portal.html>)

744

745 **Supplementary Table S7.** List of primer-pairs used for resequencing and genotyping analysis of the
746 *Phvul.006G018800* and *Phvul.008G038400* genes in the TU and Musica genotypes.

747

748 **Supplementary Table S8.** Resequencing coverage for the *Phvul.006G018800* and *Phvul.008G038400* genes.
749 Resequencing coverage is estimated based on the G19833 reference gene sequence.

750

751 **Supplementary File S1.** Multiple alignment sequences of *Phvul.006G018800* in FASTA format.

752

753 **Supplementary File S2.** Multiple alignment sequences of *Phvul.008G038400* in FASTA format.

754